

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY AND ITS THEORETICAL ASPECTS

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Abstract

Medicinal chemistry is a science that studies the methods of obtaining substances used for medical purposes, their structure, physical and chemical properties, the relationship between their chemical structure and their effect on the body, quality control methods, and what changes they undergo during storage.

Physical, chemical and physico-chemical methods are used to solve the problems facing medicinal chemistry, and these methods are widely used in the synthesis and analysis of medicinal substances.

Keywords: analysis, drug, chemistry, substance, medicine

Introduction: Medicinal chemistry occupies a central place and performs a coordinating function between other specialized disciplines of medicine, pharmacognosy, pharmacology, drug technology, drug administration and toxicological chemistry. Thus, pharmacognosy studies medicinal plant raw materials, as well as the possibilities of creating new drugs based on these raw materials, in which case the use of drug analysis methods is important. Medicinal chemistry, which studies the relationship between the structure of drug substance molecules and their effect on the body, is closely related to pharmacology. Medicinal chemistry is closely related to pharmaceutical technology, which studies the methods of obtaining pharmaceutical forms, because those pharmaceutical forms are research objects for the development of drug analysis methods. Medicinal chemistry is closely related to the organization of pharmaceutical work during the study of the problem of changes undergone by medicinal products during storage, as well as the organization of analytical services for quality control of medicines. Research methods used in medicinal chemistry are considered the basis for solving the tasks facing toxicological chemistry.

Main part: In medicine, various chemical substances are used as medicine for treatment and examination purposes. Medicinal chemistry is a science that studies the properties, sources, quality and transformations of substances used for medical purposes. The task of medicinal chemistry is to study the physical and chemical properties of medicinal substances, the methods of acquisition and purification, and to check the quality of medicines. One of the tasks facing medicinal chemistry is to study the relationship between the composition of medicinal substances and their effect on the body. Because the effect of medicinal substances on the body depends on the elements included in their composition and the order in which these elements combine to form a biologically active substance. Currently, it has been proven that the effect of inorganic medicinal substances on the body mainly depends on the cations and anions that form them. Biologically active organic compounds are related to

the structure of their molecules. It is known that medicinal substances:

1. To the source of purchase;
2. Chemical structure;
3. It is classified according to its pharmacological effect.

According to the source of purchase, medicinal substances are divided into three groups:

- synthetic (makes up 70 percent of all medicinal substances);
- semi-synthetic (obtained as a result of chemical modification of chemical compounds),
- natural (alkaloids, vitamins, hormonal, etc.).

Chemical to the structure according to medicine items inorganic (salts, oxides, complex combinations etc.) and organic (aliphatic, alicyclic, aromatic and heterocyclic combinations etc.) being two to the group is divided. Medicine of chemistry creation and development of pharmacy and of medicine development with, also chemistry of science development date with is connected. Treat yourself and of medicine creation, development date yet many ancient of times development did which is China, turkish, Ancient Greek, Egyptian countries with is related. of chemistry from the IV to the XVI century up to which is period alchemy period is called Middle century most outstanding from alchemists big turkish scientist Abu-Ali Ibn-Sina was. He himself period outstanding doctor and scientist was. Ibn Sina on medicine how many work wrote. His "Medicine of science rule" from 5 books consisting of from them two of them to medicine belongs to Ibn Sina's this work at that time the only one related to medicine work was Your work more one precious aspect and that was it for the first time in the work as medicine of the substances medical with goals application with equal, their chemical properties too given from the 16th century starting with alchemy decline to do starts in chemistry and a new direction in medicine - treatment chemistry and or iatrochemistry period started, of iatrochemistry the basis Paracelsus has put he showed that chemistry main purpose gold in hand make no, health protect should be Paracelsus impressive chemical item about

the first time as understanding gave it is different chemical items and from plants received medicine ingredients analysis make for one many innovations gave so, Paracelsus Medicine analysis the basis has put so iatro-chemistry period Medicine of chemistry creation period account is being In the 16th and 17th centuries pharmacies medicine ingredients the learner to the center had become other in other words, that time drugstores first drug chemistry laboratories was industry various production enterprises development chemistry in front of else positions which he put for chemical studies but of medicine request with enough could not For chemistry big importance which is burning and oxidation processes clarify purpose new phlogiston theory occur came to this theory basically burning and oxidize who knows of substances, things called "phlogiston" in its composition volatile, invisible and weightless special item there is also oxidation and burning during that one from the item goes away this theory of chemistry development certain degree influence done, one many chemical ingredients and of gases to the discovery road opened. Phlogiston of the theory missing aspect burning and or oxidized of the item of weight decrease not, on the contrary, the weight increase observation being was

Phlogiston of the theory wrong Lomonosov proved that for the first time has done His led by studies showed that combustion and oxidation in the processes of the air big role there is Later Lavoisier too own studies based on that one to the conclusion came He determined that oxygen forms acids and salts. Thus, the theory of oxygen, which is the basis of modern chemistry, was born. This theory created conditions for the rapid development of scientific chemistry. Pharmacists played a big role in the development of chemistry in the first half of the 19th century after the oxygen theory was created. Pharmacist Mor proposed methods of volume analysis of drugs, in general, his contribution to the development of volume analysis methods is great. In the middle of the 19th century, as a result of the development of production, pharmacies turned from chemical laboratories into centers for the preparation and sale of drugs, and the preparation of chemical substances was transferred to production. As a result of the development of organic chemistry and biological sciences at the end of the 19th century, Medicinal chemistry also began to develop rapidly. The pharmaceutical industry at that time consisted of several small pharmaceutical factories and galenic drug factories. The First World War slightly accelerated the development of the pharmaceutical industry in the country.

Thus, in 1915, a workshop for the production of medicinal preparations was opened in Moscow, next to the higher technical school, and in 1917, an alkaloid plant was launched for the first time in Russia. Recently, many new medicinal substances have been created and produced in our country. Great work has been done in the field of important vitamins, alkaloids, steroid drugs.

Medicines used in medicine can be divided into two large groups: inorganic and organic compounds. Depending on which group the drug belongs to, the

sources of their purchase also differ from each other. They use various mountain rocks, minerals, ores, mineral resources, lakes, air and sometimes industrial waste to get inorganic preparations. Organic medicines can be synthetic (that is, obtained through synthesis) and natural. The following sources are used to purchase natural preparations:

1. When processing oil and coal, many products are obtained. Some of these can be used in medicine after purification, and some can be further reprocessed into pharmaceuticals.

2. Many medicinal preparations are obtained through synthesis from intermediate products produced by various branches of the chemical industry.

3. Medicinal preparations with various active substances are prepared from medicinal plants: preparations of separate alkaloids, cardiac glycosides, flavanoids and other natural substances. Sometimes more biologically active substances are obtained through semi-synthesis based on natural substances found in plants. Examples of these are drugs based on steroids found in some plants, which resemble the hormones of the cortex layer of the adrenal glands.

4. Endocrine preparations are obtained from various organs of the animal body - endocrine glands. As raw materials, it is made from certain organs, blood, internal glands, etc. of healthy animals. is used. Insulin, heparin, etc. this applies to preparations.

5. Many medicinal preparations with a strong biological effect are obtained from some microorganisms. Among them, various antibiotic preparations can be shown. Currently, microbiological synthesis, that is, the synthesis of individual chemical compounds by a certain group of microorganisms, is used not only in the production of antibiotic substances, but also to obtain derivatives of many steroids. Microbiological synthesis differs from chemical synthesis in some cases by its low cost and selectivity.

Pharmacopoeia is a collection of national mandatory requirements and standards for the quality of medicinal preparations and medicinal raw materials. Various classifications have been proposed to study the chemical medicinal substances used in medical practice in a certain order. The dependence between the structure of medicinal substances and their pharmacological effects is their characteristic. One of the existing classifications for studying medicinal substances is the pharmacological classification. According to the pharmacological classification, medicinal substances are divided into different groups depending on their effect on the body or individual organs. For example, drugs affecting the cardiovascular system, painkillers and sedatives, sleeping pills, diuretics, antimicrobial drugs, etc. One of the shortcomings of pharmacological classification is that substances with different chemical structures and similar effects belong to one group. According to chemical classification, medicinal substances are divided into certain groups depending on their chemical structure and chemical properties. A positive aspect of chemical classification is that it explains the relationship between chemical structure and pharmacological action. This facilitates the study and

synthesis of new medicinal substances. This classification also has a missing aspect: sometimes substances that are similar in terms of their chemical structure have different pharmacological effects. For example, nicotine of acid amide (nicotinamide) and nicotine of acid diethylamide (cordiamine). Nicotinamide is a vitamin, cordiamine to work vitamin property no at the rate (from 10%). less), but his center nerve system, cardiovascular system wake-up call effect there is currently medicine ingredients to learn for mixed from classification use is done. This classification chemical and pharmacological classification positive aspects in itself concentrates. Sometimes chemical to structures according to distinguished but pharmacological to the effects according to near which is ingredients one to the group included it happens to these example natural to the ingredients similar synthetic of preparations one in the group can be studied; eg quinine and bigumal of these chemical structure is different, but physiological effect is close. Chemical classification on medicine of chemistry which he learned ingredients the following to groups divided into:

I. Inorganic medicine preparations; mainly, of the elements periodic system on grouped.

II. Organic medicine preparations; organic in chemistry acceptance done the rule on relevant to groups divided into :

1. Acyclic (aliphatic) compounds;
2. Aromatic compounds;
3. Alicyclic compounds;
4. Heterocyclic compounds.

III. Some biologically active natural compounds that are medicinal substances:

- a) alkaloids,
- b) glycosides,
- c) vitamins,
- d) hormones and hormone-like substances,
- e) with antibiotics.

Before analyzing any medicinal product, it is necessary to carefully observe its properties. Then they take an average sample for analysis. sampling mean is one of the most important issues in analysis. When checking the quality of the preparation, the average sample should correspond to the composition of the entire mass of the preparation. If the external appearance of the drug indicates that it is different, then the average sample should be taken from several different points. To take a medium sample from liquid preparations that are cloudy or sedimented, the preparation should first be shaken vigorously, and then the sample should be taken quickly. Physical, chemical, physicochemical and biological methods are used to analyze the drug and their various forms. Physical research methods. These methods consist of the following determinations and are based on the physical property of the preparation: a) solubility: the solubility of the preparation characterizes it, albeit roughly. Dissolution can also be an indicator of the degree of purity of the drug. The pharmacopoeia conditionally distinguishes the following substances according to their solubility (pharmacopoeia is a collection of national mandatory requirements and standards for the

quality of medicinal preparations and medicinal raw materials):

- "very easily soluble" means that 1 g of a substance dissolves in 1 g of a certain solvent.
- "easily soluble" means that 1 g of substance dissolves in 1 to 10 g of a certain solvent.
- "dissolves" means that 1 g of substance dissolves in 10 to 30 g of a certain solvent.
- "hardly soluble" means that 1 g of substance dissolves in 30 to 100 g of solvent.
- "slightly soluble" means that 1 g of substance dissolves in 100 to 1000 g of solvent.
- "very little soluble" means that 1 g of substance dissolves in 1000 to 10000 g of solvent.
- "practically insoluble", i.e. 1g of substance dissolves in more than 10000g of solvent.

Some preparations dissolve gradually, that is, it takes more than 10 minutes for them to dissolve. For such preparations, heating in a water bath up to 30 and shaking for 2-3 minutes is allowed. If a certain temperature is not indicated for the dissolution of preparations, dissolution is assumed at 20° C.

b) melting temperature: of substance slub completely liquid to become don't pass temperature his melting temperature account is being appointment for taken the first liquid in matter of drops done coming of melting the beginning of the article absolutely fluid still to pass to work of melting the end account is done. When melted disintegrating ingredients for their which in temperature suddenly change melting temperature and either fragmentation temperature account is being Chemical clean, individual ingredients absolutely clean and dry when certain in temperature and either many slight temperature between (0.5 – 1,0) melts. Most cases this temperature melting point is called item wet and in the composition various mixtures if, his melting temperature down falls most organic ingredients for melting temperature typical one is an indicator, of substances melting the temperature appointment by doing their identity and cleanliness certain degree to check possible. v) boiling temperature: at normal pressure of substance beginning and final boiling temperature between which is interval boiling temperature account is being Do not boil the temperature appointment make for distillation without doing use they do do not boil at this time temperature as, all distillation during stable the rest of the thermometer that it shows temperature is taken initial boiling temperature whom so temperature intended 5 drops to the receiver that is caught fluid get fired Final boiling so temperature intended to the receiver that is caught 95% of the liquid let it pass Above shown from studies other, physical study methods of preparations special weight, transparency, colors determination, in preparations volatile of substances and of water determination and so on. Belongs to Chemical research methods. Medicine of the substances quality to check for chemical methods main place holds Pharmacopoeia after roasting after stay and your ashes the appointment gives Inorganic of compounds roasting as a result residue is taken. Organic of the merger burning as a result to work received residue ash is called Many preparations for residue and your ashes quantity in the pharmacopoeia is shown. This indicator of the drug

cleanliness, sometimes identity proof who did of factors is one The environment of reaction - pH determination big importance which is a check. The environment reaction hydrogen of ions from the hardness it depends this check as a result environment sour, basic and either neutral characteristic to be appointment is done. Neutral in solutions pH=7, acid pH 7 in solutions, alkaline solutions have a pH of 7. Determine the pH make for colorimetric method and potentiometric of methods use is being Colorimetric method of indicators of color of hydrogen at a given pH of ions activity from the effect to change based on This method with destination of indicators and standard buffer of solutions with help instead of is given. Potentiometric of pH by method determination, two from the electrode consisting of which is of the element electricity movement to measure the force (EHQ). based on From these electrodes one indicator it was his potential appointment which is hydrogen of ions from the hardness it depends Second electrode standard has been comparison is for him potential known it happens Comparison electrodes whom calomel and silver chloride electrodes is processed. Determine the pH make for indicator electrode whom hydrogen, quinhydrone and glass electrodes application is done. Currently this principle on working and determine the pH make for which is special devices – pH meters application is done. Physico-chemical research methods. Physico-chemical methods medicine of the substances analysis, research that one of substances and either From them received certain of the product physical-chemical properties based on Physico-chemical methods medicine of the substances identity, purity and the amount appointment make possible. Because of this many little time, less amount checked item spent is being and the majority cases many exactly results is taken. In recent years physical-chemical methods separately medicine preparations and either medicine mixtures analysis make for wide use is being Physico-chemical methods the following study methods refers to:

- Optical methods. Optical methods analysis which is of substance and either his product which is of substances optical properties based on optical analysis methods refractometry, polarimetry, photometry belongs to,

- Electrochem methods. To this group potentiometry, conductometry and polarography belongs to,

- Chromatographic analysis methods.

Mix it up in the composition which is of substances physical and either chemical properties dependent as two phase between by dividing separately to the components separation of chromatography the basis organize is doing in chromatography of the mixture to the components separation adsorbent and of the solvent from nature it depends With that related as of chromatography the following types there are: a) adsorption with chromatography b) ion exchanger chromatography; v) distributive chromatography; q) gas and gas-liquid chromatography Biological research methods. Some medicine preparations above shown of methods help with appointment by doing to be satisfied it doesn't happen. because this methods of the drug quality and biological full coverage of the effect to do doesn't know so cases biological research methods use they do of

these methods help with chemical reactions based on easily disintegrating and structure clearly without items analysis they do Biological methods of preparations pharmacological influence force characterize is doing Biological destination animals and either sometimes their certain members on is being conducted. Antibiotics in the appointment to work certain from microorganisms use they do biological methods of research the results influence units with they show checked of the drug influence force standard of preparations effect with comparison they do State in the pharmacopoeia one many endocrine drugs, heart glucoside drugs, antibiotics, some of vitamins quality biological of methods help with is checked.

Conclusion: In general, which in the country production from being made dependent regardless of, each one medicine of the vehicle quality international requirements suitable should come international requirements the whole World Healthcare Organization (WHO) medicine of preparations to the quality control in the field of the program inseparable composition part being, relevant in the documents opposite is made. Note where as, international scale as well too various countries medicine of preparations quality regulator legal document It is a pharmacopoeia.

In our country medicine production which, medicine who keeps them the examiner and who works each one enterprise DF instructions for is the law. State Separately in the Pharmacopoeia (DF). pertaining to preparations with requirements as well as medicines analysis make for needed which is physical-chemical, chemical and bacteriological methods, respectively reagents, indicators, titrated solutions, standards and necessary tables description has been done. In Pharmacopoeia of drugs main names so it has been shown that first on the ground let's own it case of the cation name, second on the ground noun in case of noun which is of the anion name is given, of anions names oxygenated of acids to salts - as and is, without oxygen of acids in salts and - idum of the last suffixes with help arises. Oxides for international latin names use done; oxydum – oxide, peroxydum – peroxide, hydroxydum – hydroxide. Industry by production which is all medicine of means quality DF and Temporary pharmacopoeia of articles (MFM), as well within the republic technical of the conditions instructions relevant as should be checked.

Note make it is necessary that Azerbaijan Republic in the 20th century from 1920 to 1991 up to the past Soviet Socialist Republics of the country of the Union (USSR). in the composition ally republic was. Including in the former USSR In Azerbaijan SSR State VI-XI editions of Pharmacopoeia in effect has been, currently that one of the state legal successor which is Russia in the Federation and XII edition legal is in force.

Right now In the Republic International Pharmacopoeia, Europe Pharmacopoeia, American Pharmacopoeia, Big Britain and Russia State From the pharmacopoeia wide use is being International Pharmacopoeia (Pharmacopoea Internationalis) by WHO is prepared and edition is done. International Pharmacopoeia creation of the world all in their countries medicine of means to the quality and naming unit requirements to

be placed conditions created . International Pharmacopoeia for the first time in 1951 edition was made, currently the IV edition legal is in force. This is the Pharmacopoeia separately of states from pharmacopoeias main different aspect so his requirements legislator not a recommendation is characteristic.

International Pharmacopoeia National Pharmacopoeias preparation for one base account is being Own Pharmacopoeia without and or medicine means basically else from countries import who did countries International Pharmacopoeia management whom use they do In view let's say the UN member of the 150 states that of only 33 countries own Pharmacopoeia there are, then the drugs to the quality of control in improvement International Pharmacopoeia importance undeniable which is it seems International Pharmacopoeia with regional and national pharmacopoeias also operate shows.

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